

How Information Management can help smooth the transition towards i-voting

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ABSTRACT

This report provides an analysis of the digital transformation of the public sector as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic, in particular the transition towards i-voting. The aim was to analyse how the tools and practises used in the Information Management discipline can be of help in this transition. The insights derived and discussed in this paper from the IT Governance, Business Process Integration, and Cybersecurity perspective are the need for trust, integrity but also transparency. The paper will provide suggestions on how the transition should be approached, and how several practices from these three perspectives can be used to implement solutions to the existing obstacles. The goal of this paper is to provide suggestions for further action or research on this topic, and to make sure that the transition to i-voting will happen as smoothly as possible when the time comes.

Keywords

i-voting, government

INTRODUCTION

Through this report, we want to analyse the digital transformation in the public sector. More specifically we want to examine the option of i-voting (voting from home/remote with a device which is connected to the Internet). We were motivated by the fact that the majority of our group will have an election during a pandemic. Therefore, we searched for solutions on how we can still execute our human right – the right to vote – without posing a threat to others and ourselves. We are aware that mail ballots (postal voting) are a secure and convenient solution to solve this problem, however, we thrive for digital solutions. Therefore, we decided to look further into i-voting. This report does not focus on elections in specific countries or municipalities, as these could have very individual rules. We wanted to dedicate our interests to

generally applicable international standards for elections (International law such as ICCPR). However, we sometimes emphasize countries as it is easier to explain our ideas. I-voting has been considered by many countries, however, not many gave it a try because of either security or public concerns. There are a few exemptions, a few countries which test i-voting on a small scale. But a country which is worth mentioning is Estonia, they developed an i-voting system in 2005 and it is widely accepted. In the last election 44% voted via this option (e-estonia, 2020). For this paper, we do not consider the legal or ethnic context we focus on the Information Management side. Therefore, we want to describe it from IT-Governance, Business Process Integration as well as Cyber Security – perspective.

RESEARCH

Objective

Our objective for this paper is to find answers for whether countries should implement an i-voting system for upcoming elections or not. In the 2000s many countries experimented with i-voting but finally didn't implement it on a bigger scale. Some countries implemented it on a small scale but didn't expand it further, either for security, legal or ethical reasons. For most countries this "experiment" is some time ago, the technology which we have now is more advanced than back then, which could make the system more secure. There is one country (Estonia) which has been using i-voting for 15 years already. Other countries could learn from their system and also implement it. We want to analyse i-voting systems with the help of Information Management tools. Therefore, our research question for this paper is: "How Information Management can help smooth the transition towards i-voting?"

Approach

In order to answer our research question “How Information Management can help smooth the transition towards i-voting?”, we want to focus on management tools for the topics of IT Governance, Business Process Integration, Cyber Security and Risk Management. As mentioned previously we will focus on a general statement in accordance with international standards rather than country-specific legislation. For this report, we will focus on all three levels (federal, regional local) of the public sector, as all levels will have elections and the procedures are similar. We will not focus on public organizations as they are usually not required for elections. This work will not include expert interviews or surveys. We decided to focus on literature review as we want to emphasize only the technical aspects and leave out other aspects as the scope of this report is very limited. The data collected will on the one hand consist out of academic research and on the other hand out of trustworthy internet sources.

GOVERNMENT SECTOR

As mentioned previously the focus of this report lies in the public sector, because elections are usually held by different levels of governments. Usually, the government has three levels. First and most influential is the federal level, this is the government of a country. The next level is regional, this is for example the government of a state or a province. The local level is the last level, these are municipalities or counties. Furthermore, the public sector comprises organizations that are owned and operated by the government. The public sector exists to provide services for its citizens. In general organizations in the public sector do not seek to generate profit. The public sector's main difference to the private sector is that they do not have a customer per se, as the people usually cannot choose from which government they get served. The citizens usually only have one passport and, therefore, they cannot choose from which (federal) government they receive services. The public sector is usually funded through raised money for example through taxes, fees or financial transfers from another level of government (privacysense, n.d.). The market size of the public sector differs by country as some countries decide to have many people employed by the public sector others decide to employ as little as possible. Some countries have privatized parts of their duties such as education, human & social services or public transport, so these countries will have less market size. As we base our paper on a general approach and not a specific country, we cannot name specific key players as they are very different and dependent on the country.

Digitalization

It is said that digitalization is key for the future of business in many sectors. This also applies to the public sector. Many citizens and businesses expect government information to be available 24/7 online at low or no cost. According to a McKinsey report, the potential of government digitalization could free up to 1 trillion dollars per year. In 2014 already more than 130 countries had offered some of their services online. However, digitalization in the public sector is a challenge. A change process in the public sector is more likely to experience cost overruns and these processes are also more likely to be delivered after the scheduled deployment date. Additionally, the public sector must cope with management issues such as organizational mandates and constituencies as well as maintaining strategic continuity as well as political administration changes (Dilmegani, Korkmaz, Lundqvist, 2014).

COVID-19

The pandemic has not spared the public sector, it was also heavily affected in the previous month. On the one hand, the governments will be left with higher debt as well as concerns about globalisation as well as inequality. On the other hand, the lockdown has accelerated collaborative technologies such as remote work and citizen behaviour may change (Deloitte 2020). This crisis can be seen as a chance to accelerate digital transformation, therefore, we think i-voting could be interesting for many countries.

ANALYSIS

IT-Governance and Strategic Sourcing

COVID-19 has drastically changed the IT governance structure of the government, which will be discussed based on the case of remote online voting according to the five key IT decisions that need to be made.

Principles

A big difference between the private and the public sector is the nature of interaction with the customer, which in the public sector is determined by relevant laws or historic practice (Dudovskiy, 2013). Everyone needs a passport and, ideally, everyone needs to vote. This is why the IT used in the government should be user friendly, so it is accessible to everyone. The government also handles a lot of sensitive data, making security, privacy and transparency important. The IT used to make government services, like i-voting available, should take these principles into account. For this,

the government should be responsible and held accountable.

Architecture

The various products and services that the government offers are linked to citizens. The data surrounding these practises are centred around the individual citizens. It is important to know which citizen is qualified to receive what services and products, however with citizen's votes it would be slightly different. It is important that data is collected on the fact that a citizen voted, to make sure their vote only counts once, but information on what they voted should not be available. The individual votes should be able to be aggregated, thus standardization is needed to achieve this.

Infrastructure

The citizen needs to register to vote in order for the government to make sure that someone's vote only counts once. However, once the citizen registers to vote, they lose their anonymity, thus there is an authentication problem. What they actually voted needs to be anonymised, so it is untraceable who voted what. The citizen needs to log into the voting system with the same credentials used for other government services, so the vote can be linked to the citizen. Then they need to fill in the electronic ballot and submit their vote. At submission, the fact that they voted needs to be registered, so their vote only counts once but what they voted needs to be anonymised before it is sent to the tallying system, where the votes are aggregated and counted. This process needs to be secure and transparent, for which the government is responsible.

Business application needs

The systems that the government uses for their services are differentiated by the higher need for security and privacy because of the sensitive information they deal with. This is also the case for the online voting system. It is not new, many talent-shows use online voting systems to choose the winner of a particular program. This means that the software the government needs in order to be able to make remote online voting a reality is not that unique, which would allow them to outsource it. What makes it more difficult is the need for security and transparency (Benny, 2020). The firm that develops and manages the system should be held accountable for the security of the system as well as the processes behind it. This should be subjected to extensive auditing, to make sure everything is secure. The government should be responsible for making sure the audit is done properly.

Investment and prioritization

There are a lot of aspects in the digital transformation of the government that deserve prioritising and the funds to make it happen. Other than investing in the means to continue to make it possible to work from home and have virtual meetings to keep the day-to-day operations running, remote online voting should not be too far down the list of priorities. It would increase the value of the government as remote online voting could make voting more accessible to citizens than the physical voting system. Once implemented correctly it saves time both for the people voting and for the people counting the votes.

It is evident that a lot has changed in this sector and in particular in the area of voting. Due to this, each of the decisions needs to be examined again and transformation is needed to keep up with these changes.

Business Process Integration

From a BPI perspective, the COVID-19 pandemic has substantially increased interest in the field, and it has gotten much more attention in the public and corporate world. Companies have been pushed over the technology tipping point, and this has transformed business forever (McKinsey, 2020). Private companies amongst many industries, as well as the public sector, have increased the amount of processes and services they perform online. Because of social distancing and people working from home they have been forced to digitize in some shape or form. Late 2020 and early 2021 there will be presidential / state elections all across the world, and this might be the right point in time for I-voting to gain traction within the public. This section will elaborate on processes that have to be in place to make remote electronic voting a reality. It will mention the most important differences between the current and the prospected system, and provide suggestions for implementation.

The topic of this paper, the potential shift from the offline voting system to an electronic system, can by itself be viewed as a process being integrated into our digital citizenship. Consider Dutch citizens, who are using DigID to identify themselves when making arrangements on the internet, such as with the government, educational institutes, healthcare institutions or your pension fund. DigID is increasingly being used for various purposes, which reflects the increase in public processes which the people are supposed to do online. Voting could be next. But the trust, transparency and integrity factor is much more of an issue with the voting process than it is in the processes covered with DigID. In fact, they can be assumed to be the underlying reason for why we are still not voting electronically.

A lack of trust and integrity among the public.

As mentioned before, one of the priorities of this paper is to not dig too deep into the ethical discussion surrounding voting systems, and narrow down the scope to the Information Management discipline. For this section however, looking at the processes which are in place for the current voting system, it is inevitable to touch upon the ethical perspective. The electronic voting system should be viewed as a complementary option, not as a substitute. People who truly want to vote offline should be given that option, as it is the most inclusive and non-controversial way forward in this discussion.

The obstacles of trust and transparency could potentially be tackled by integrating processes or activities which should be considered necessary in order to increase the level of trust in an electronic system among the voters, and to minimize the loss of transparency as compared to the current voting system. Past attempts have been made to introduce this new voting system. In the past the Dutch government stopped pursuing this avenue. As Kohno et al. (2004) mention, the integrity of the election process is fundamental to the integrity of democracy itself. One of the first problems with the introduction of remote electronic voting concerns the trust towards the use of technology and information management in a process as fundamental as our voting system. The underlying reason is that there will be a loss in transparency throughout the process. People will raise concerns about the integrity of their data and the vote as a whole. In order to tackle this problem thought needs to be given to potential processes which can increase either the trust of the people, the transparency of the voting process, or a combination of both. Voters would be more supportive of this transition if they would receive a confirmation of their vote, but not get insight into the whole voting pool. It should also be integer, without the possibility of someone reviewing their vote in a later stage. Such a proof of vote would increase the corruption opportunities.

Another point of discussion is the increase in costs, depending on the extent towards which the system is able to be centralized. By implementing this new system while also maintaining the old system there needs to be a higher budget available. This discussion can however be rapidly concluded by arguing that one cannot put a price on the fundamentals of our democracy.

The two sides to this story are that while people like the ease of online processes, they are also sceptical towards the security and privacy matters. Whereas COVID-19 increases the need for ease and remote tasks, the scepticism towards the privacy and integrity of electronic voting is also much higher than it is with other processes which have been

digitized (e.g. DigID).

Cyber Security

Considering the voter's need for security and trust from a Cybersecurity point of view, the main goal is to establish a trustful relationship with the voter through the design and security of the system. Besides the Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability (CIA hereafter) requirements, the process also has to be transparent for the general public. On the other hand, the vote must always be anonymous, and impossible to be traced. Every vote may only be counted once, and the system must count each eligible ballot. The concept of non-repudiation becomes important for our system. In this section we will discuss the concept of remote electronic voting from a security perspective. We will assess risks and probabilities of attacks, and provide suggestions for how to minimize or how to overcome them.

The integrity of voting systems is a very interesting and actual topic of discussion. In the U.S presidential debate in September 2020 it also led to heated arguments, while remote electronic voting was not even touched upon! Every voting system is subject to potential risks. A risk assessment matrix was made to assess the risks related to remote electronic voting. It proposes that the impact of potential threats is measured based on the relevance that they could have on the general population confidence. Trust seems to be the pillar on which the acceptance of a digital transformation of different democratic processes lie. Therefore it is important that the same is reflected in the proposed model, which would not only mean assessing the security features in depth but also materialising the assessment results. The processes will only be trusted and consequently, generally accepted when the depth of security is transparent and indeed apparent to the users and the candidates.

According to a conference paper (Kohno et al., 2004), the cyber security risks in elections (U.S.A in the conference paper) are nothing new, the current systems in place are also susceptible to all kinds of attacks; smart-card cloning, tampering with the ballot definitions and cyber fraud. The proposed voting system should be user-friendly and should permit the users, without discrimination, to exercise their right to vote. It should take into account all the risks and measures discussed above in order to be effective.

COVID-19 has evidently disrupted most business functions and government functions fare no better. As a result, these processes have either been modified or digitally transformed. According to a report by KPMG Netherlands (KPMG, 2020), since the start of COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a rise in remote connections and increased use of personal devices. More internet traffic and therewith more online vulnerability, directly translates into a higher need for cybersecurity practices. If voting was to be digitally transformed, the system in place would have to be robust, state of the art. Naturally, in order to develop such a system, the governments would have to incur huge costs. However, the advantages of an ideal system, the ease of access and management in particular would show the worth. The system would have to be tested in-depth in real life situations. One could argue that the person or the place storing the keys/blueprint of the system, could be corrupted or tampered with. This is nothing but an instance of the cyber related risks, complications the system would have.

Remote electronic voting carries many challenges from a cybersecurity perspective. The largest challenge probably lies in public opinion. The people which are against this system either do not trust such a fundamental process to be executed by technology, or they are aware of the cybersecurity dangers. Since this paper aims to provide suggestions as to how remote electronic voting could become a reality, Appendix A contains a security report, digging further into the risk assessment and providing a hypothetical cybersecurity model. The COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the ongoing discussion and dissatisfaction with the current system, are potential tailwinds for remote electronic voting to gain more popularity.

DISCUSSION

As in all studies we have several challenges and limitations. Especially taking into account that it became evident that there is not a clear, single solution to answer our research question as to what extent the Information Management tools and practises can stimulate the transition towards a remote online voting system.

Regarding the basic limitations, it is not in this paper's purpose to attempt arguing whether an electronic voting system is desirable or not. However, the COVID-19 situation had brought back the interest in deploying this kind of solution. Therefore, the research question became relevant assessing how rigid processes traditionally related with physical activities, such as registering in a

municipality, could be implemented online. Especially in a relevant scenario such as democratic election process.

We could acknowledge that the main specially relevant characteristics of implementing this kind of solution is strictly related to the citizens of a determined country of municipality, as they would have to accept the government decision as it is. Therefore, the concept of 'trust' became essential to the successful deployment of an electronic voting solution.

Assigning responsibility and accountability to different groups, as has been done in the IT Governance chapter could stimulate this trust in the system that would eventually be developed. To stimulate this trust to an even greater extent, simultaneous physical voting could also be present and training/assistance could be provided, respectively.

Regarding the Business integration perspective, trust once again is important as it is needed to gain traction within the public sector and the public opinion. Several tools could be used to map out the specific processes needed to ensure this. UML diagrams are useful for process mapping and making sure no excess parties along the process.

As for the cybersecurity perspective, trust is obviously a big part of this. If the system is not secure it would definitely lower citizen's trust in it, making the transition to a remote online voting system. Acknowledgement of the various risk factors and their impact as well as finding controls to bring these risks down will make the system more secure, increasing citizen's trust and once again making the transition towards a remote online voting system an easier one.

All in all it would be safe to say that the tools and practises used in Information Management can ease the transition. Once again, this paper is not focussed on whether or not such a transition should or should not take place, but on should it be decided, what would help.

Finally, it would be worthy to mention that this project gave us the opportunity to merge the knowledge acquired from the different courses of the Information Management programme into a joint effort to understand the peculiarities of applying it to a real case scenario.

CONCLUSION

Remote electronic voting has been a topic of interest for many years, but it never made a breakthrough. Estonia is the only country that has been using a remote electronic voting system, and the system has

been gaining more traction over the years, currently making up the majority of the voters (E-Estonia, 2020). Globally, general attitude towards the matter is critical, but the COVID-19 pandemic could play a positive role. The BPI, ITG and Cybersecurity perspectives have all provided valuable insights as to how this process can be realized and which obstacles stand in the way of its success. Furthermore, given the general digitalization trends and the never ending discussion surrounding the current voting system, a switch to remote electronic voting seems only a matter of time. When the time comes, the system has to be thoroughly tested and improved along the way. When it is implemented, it should be used in small-scale elections first, perhaps regional elections, in order to test its functionality as well as to build trust with the general public.

APPENDIX A

Context and security objectives

Elections are undoubtedly the most important part of a democracy. Naturally, the integrity of democracy relies on the integrity of elections, whether online or otherwise. Any proposed remote electronic voting system must be sufficiently robust, compressible and transparent that the stakeholders (voters and candidates) can accept the results. As there are complications involved in adapting rigid processes to a digital environment, it becomes vital that the security objectives of our system are also rigidly established. The main goal is to build trust in relationships with both the design of the system and the democratic processes. For that, the need is to not only fulfil the Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability (CIA hereafter) requirements but also make this process transparent to the general public. With these objectives in mind, the following are the security objectives for our system:

(C)-Confidentiality: Secrecy of voting is a core necessity for a democratic system. The cast must always be anonymous, and the information should not be accessible to anyone. The anonymity is to ensure the safety of the voter when voting for or against a malevolent candidate. Since there would be no evidence of the vote cast, it would be impossible to purchase votes.

(I)-Integrity: Every vote must only be counted once, and the system must count each eligible ballot. Therefore, the concept of non-repudiation becomes integral in our system.

(A)-Availability:

1. All eligible persons must be able to vote.
2. The general population should have access to the general output of the elections.
3. Transparency: Different stakeholders/individuals should be able to access their vote and check the counting process (mostly journalists and the different political parties involved). However, it must be ensured that the ballots cannot be traced back to their identities as this would challenge the confidentiality of the system.

Perform risk assessments

Any voting system, whether online or otherwise, is subject to potential risks. Take Florida 2001 presidential election, for instance, the inadequacy of the voting machine risked the integrity of the election as people could not vote. An electronic voting system is vulnerable to two kinds of attacks, a) someone with physical access to the database or server; b) intercepting the data while it is being transmitted (Kohno et al., 2004). Such a system would also be susceptible to physical risks (mentioned below but are out of scope for this report):

Physical risks:

1. Physical damage to databases that storage vote (A, I)
2. Human related risks (A, I, C)

System risks:

1. Vote counted more than once (I)

Cyber risks:

1. Information leak of individual votes (C)
2. Inability to vote during the election period, eg. (DoS) Denial of Service attacks (A)
3. Tampering with the user's system: A user's system could be hacked in different ways for instance via keyloggers or remote access, the confidentiality of the vote can be compromised.
4. Tampering with the system's client: System's client is the interface which is accessible to the user where he/she logs in and casts the vote. This interface would obviously be well encrypted, however, if an unauthorised user with malicious intent were to gain access to it, it could compromise the integrity of the whole system.
5. Impersonating a legitimate voting system:

If someone were to create a fake voting system which would send the votes to a shell back-end server, this would not only compromise the confidentiality of the vote but would also impact the tally.

6. Cryptographic issues with voting and auditing: Logs and actual records of both the voting and auditing would be encrypted before being stored. Therefore it would be important to ensure the accessibility of the keys and access to the database.

Risk attitude, from a business point of view, is ultimately a decision that depends on the cost-efficiency of the implementation of different new controls. However, our study case is linked with rigid processes that could not be undermined by an information leak. Either the impact has to be minimized, or the probability has to be decreased in order to not surpass the risk attitude acceptance of six (as shown in our risk matrix). In this case, all the squares that are higher than six would not be acceptable for our model.

Risk matrix:

Impact: 5 - All core values of the election process have been compromised and the results are nullified. The election must happen again.

Impact: 4 - A high proportion of the population would doubt the reliability of the election process, and it is likely that the votes were either repeated or miscalculated. The election might happen again.

Impact: 3 - A considerable amount of the population would doubt about the reliability and accuracy of the election process.

Impact: 2 - A low proportion of the population would doubt about the reliability and accuracy of the election process.

Impact: 1 - Flaws would not impact a significant portion of the population trust.

Due to unavailability of the data regarding the likelihood of the above risk events occurring, we

would base the probability of an attack on the resources that are required to carry it:

Probability 1: The resources needed to deploy an attack are extensive and you will need physical access to the databases or infrastructure.

Probability 2: The resources needed to deploy an attack are extensive, but you won't need physical access to the databases. For instance, governments.

Probability 3: The resources and the collaboration needed to deploy a successful attack could only be achieved by large companies.

Probability 4: A large organized group of IT professionals could deploy a successful attack.

Probability 5: A small group of IT professionals could deploy a successful attack.

The above risk matrix combined with the risks identified and the core processes below would be our blueprint for designing an online voting system. Core processes:

1. **Call for election:** Citizens are informed about the election process.
2. **Facilitate the vote casting:** Providing the system with which the users will vote. The system will take the ballot and send it for audit.
3. **Verify integrity:** The authenticity and validity of voters and their votes are verified.
4. **Auditing of votes:** The votes are audited and anonymised.
5. **Publish the results:** The results are published.

As an exemplification we could describe the risk assessment process of a DoS attack on the internet servers used to cast the vote. Therefore, an attack that affects the vote casting process. Let's assess a likelihood of '5', as a little group of IT professionals could successfully launch an attack and an impact of 3 assuming that the trust of a considerable amount of population would decrease if they could not cast their vote in several hours. The risk would be assessed as follows:

- Risk = Impact*Likelihood;
- Risk = 3*5 = 15

Therefore, a way to mitigate this problem would be increasing the resilience of the system implementing different substitution servers in order to easily recover from an attack of those characteristics, decreasing the impact on the trust of the population as they would be able to cast their vote in little time.

After implementing the control measure the new risk could be assessed as follows:

- Risk = $1 * 5 = 5$

Thanks to this control measure the risk taken could be considered 'acceptable' for such a rigid process as a democratic election one.

System analysis

It is of the utmost importance that any proposed system abides by the rules of democracy defined earlier. Therefore the system must also adapt to different potential user groups. For instance, one of these user groups could be people over a certain age or people with a disability.

For example, a hypothetical voting system by the name of Make Voting Great Again (MVGA)

In MVGA there would be two identical lists of eligible voters, list A and list B. MVGA could facilitate remote voting where the user would use their digital ID to log in to a VPN server. The access keys for the VPN server would differ based on the constituency in which one is voting. This would ensure the integrity of the votes in other constituencies when one of the constituencies is compromised. The vote cast would then be encrypted with a composite of a common central key and the constituency key and then be transmitted to the central server. The server would then decrypt the data and make an audit. When a user (ID: A) casts a vote, his vote is added to the list B and his personal details are removed, therefore anonymising the vote. This vote then could not be tracked to the user. Therefore, in the end, list B would contain all the users which were eligible to vote but did not as well as the anonymous votes. The data store would be encrypted and then stored in the database.

As discussed in BPI, in order for a successful implementation, all groups must be able to exercise their rights equally. If a cybersecurity system were to adapt to these conditions, it must have the following characteristics:

1. **Access Management:** An access control system is required to ensure that nobody else could link the casted vote with the voter. In cybersecurity, practically every voter cannot have a private key. Therefore, for this process to be viable, the state must have an electronic authentication system already in place, such as DigiD in the Netherlands.
2. **Secure voting network:** When accessing the internet to cast their vote, the voters must do it in a protected environment.

Therefore, a virtual private network would seem like a proper solution to this problem. In order to ensure the integrity of the voting process, a symmetrical key with the public key of the e-ballot and the private key of the voter would allow them to do so.

3. **Ensuring the Integrity of the vote:** E-ballot would help us to separate in different layers and with different public keys, individual voters and the state...
4. **Ensuring Availability of the voting system:** Back-up: In case there is any kind of problem with the database, it is a best practice to have in place a separate back-up database.
5. **Capacity Management:** We should ensure that during the voting process everybody would be able to cast their vote. Therefore, we would need enough processing capacity for the maximum voters to vote and consult their votes at the same time.
6. **Ensuring Confidentiality of the vote:**
 - Encryption and Decryption processes: Even if the data is leaked it would be leaked encrypted with different keys, therefore it would be complicated to know.
 - After counting the information should be destroyed
 - In order to ensure confidentiality, a modified Bell Lapadula model would become handy if we implement e-voting ballots by the constituency with a Public Key (PK), building at the same time a middle layer between the election results and the voter.

Recommendation

According to research, remote e-voting systems are gaining popularity, not so much for general government elections but for associations and institutes. For parliamentary elections, however, such a system would have to be well defined and assessed. Therefore it becomes imperative to determine and follow standardised protocols. One such international criterion is the Common Criteria for Information Technology Security Evaluation (CC). In CC, functional and security requirements are defined using Protection Profiles (PP). The PP is essential to determine as well as enforce a minimum set of requirements which an electronic voting system must follow. The CC establishes evaluation depth by measuring evaluation assurance level (EAL) ranging from 1 (low-depth evaluation) to 7 (intensive evaluation). The assessment is crucial as it increases the trustworthiness of the system's security features in question, thereby bringing the system closer to following the security objectives defined above. Systems facilitating a rigid application such as voting require a more semi-

formal/formal description of the system design; therefore, the assurance level 5+ is required. It is important to note that the EAL does vouch for the security of the system itself but the level of testing. EAL5+ would ensure that the system follows a more modular approach, which can considerably be analysed better. (Bräunlich & Grimm, 2013, p. 12)

Conclusion

Initially, remote voting through the internet might seem like a distant reality however, Estonia is already leading the way by offering 99% of their public services online, including voting. The system in Estonia has been active since 2005 and has saved over 11000 working per election ever since (Enterprise Estonia, 2020).

Cybersecurity still remains an important aspect of the system. Therefore it is important to have an ecosystem where these services could potentially interact. For instance in the Netherlands, if the DigiD system could be applied to everyone, this would then serve as a potential backbone for the identification of voters. This is just an instance, and there are many more. There would also be issues where people would question the integrity of the process and not the system itself. For instance how do you tackle votes being bought or coerced? Estonia's solution to the problem is to allow voters to change their vote for 10 days during the election period. This would allow voters to change their vote later. Evidently, the solutions to complicated cybersecurity processes could, at times, be very simple and online parliamentary voting could be more of a reality than some might think.

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